

The homœopathic treatment of asthma and allergies

K. R. WALLACE, MB, BCHIR, MFHOM

It is particularly with the miasm known as psora that we are concerned in treating allergic disease. One of the most important characteristics of psora is the inheritance of a tendency to develop certain diseases and I need hardly remind you of the strong family history of one or more of the triad of asthma, eczema and hay fever. This is the first important approach and homœopaths will frequently use remedies which are classed as antipsoric, notably *Psorinum* and *Sulphur*; other important antipsoric remedies are *Lycopodium*, *Calc. carb.*, *Silicea*, *Natrum muriaticum* and *Arsenicum*.

It is also held that the use of constitutional remedies can improve allergic illness. The subject of constitutional remedies is the most important and at the same time the most difficult for the newcomer to homœopathy.

Thirdly it is possible to desensitize patients to known allergens, using homœopathic doses of the allergens. The obvious examples are house dust mite, grass pollens, animal dander, moulds and so on. Homœopathic preparations can be made of any allergen and acute reactions to their administration have never been recorded.

These three approaches to homœopathic treatment are common to the triad of atopic illness, but one or more of these approaches may be considered in any particular case and desensitization can even have a dramatic effect on its own, as will be shown below.

My approach to the treatment of asthma is summarized in Table 1. You will see that both prevention and treatment of attacks are considered. The components have been listed to show the approach to the treatment of each of these, not to state the obvious. The general approach considers antipsoric remedies, constitutional remedies and homœopathic desensitization, but when we come to the asthmas which may follow prior infection with respiratory viruses and so on, homœopathy is able to provide a group of remedies known as the nosodes. These are potencies of material from infectious diseases containing the causative organism, or sometimes potencies of the cultured organism only, which are used to prevent episodes of infection or for clearing up the remote (in time) effect of infection. Thus homœopaths use common cold tablets given at regular intervals, especially during the winter months, in the belief that this reduces the frequency of that infection, and may also give a dose of the nosode *Tuberculinum* occasionally for prevention, for clearly a nosode derived from tuberculous lung is homœopathic to patients who

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TABLE 1 Homœopathic treatment of asthma

Prevention of attacks

Components

- 1 Allergy
- 2 Infection
- 3 Stress

1 Similar approach as to allergies in general:

- Antipsoric remedies
- Constitutional remedies
- Desensitization using suspected allergens

2 Use of Nosodes

- Prevention of infection
- Treatment of infection

3 'Psychotherapy'

- Use of constitutional remedy

Treatment of attacks

Choice of remedy on basis of exact symptoms

Examples: *Arsenicum*, *Ipecac.*, *Natrum sulph.*

have episodes of productive cough and pyrexia, etc. That is one approach, but a nosode should also be considered where a patient has only wheezed since an episode of an infectious illness like whooping cough (*Pertussin*) or measles (*Morbillinum*). As far as stress is concerned I will say very little, but perhaps emphasize that homœopathy teaches you to look at each patient as a unique individual, hence the constitutional approach. A variety of methods may be used to reduce the impact of stress, be it psychotherapy, hypnosis, meditation, relaxation, etc, but in addition the use of constitutional remedies should be considered, based on the totality of psychological and physical characteristics.

In the prevention of asthma the homœopathic approach is undoubtedly highly rewarding. When we come to the treatment of asthmatic attacks, we are on much more difficult ground. Not because homœopathic remedies do not work, but for several other reasons. There is the problem of recording the exact symptoms of a patient during an attack in order to identify the remedy. Much more serious problems arise because many patients are far-flung, are on other doctor's lists, and it is not usually possible to see them at all during the acute attack. To me this raises considerable ethical problems. If, however, one can give your individual attention to your own patient, one is fully justified in the initial administration of remedies. A thumb-nail sketch of three remedies with their main indications may illustrate the method of selecting the appropriate drug. (Table 2)

Doctors new to homœopathy may think that the time modalities in the choice of a remedy are a little curious and fanciful. Whoever heard of a choice between one conventional drug or another according to the times of onset or exacerbation of an illness, but this time thread will be found to run right through homœopathy and I suggest an analogy between this conception and really very recent work linking the efficacy of drug action with the body's chronological rhythm.

I would like to advise comparative newcomers to homœopathy to seriously

TABLE 2 Examples of remedies used in the treatment of asthma

<i>Arsenicum</i>	Onset 12-2 a.m. Must get out of bed Very chilly patient Wants hot drinks, hot applications Restless Fearful Anxious
<i>Ipecac.</i>	Violent sneezing Coughing and retching Worse for warmth Better for open air
<i>Natrum sulph.</i>	Onset 4-5 a.m. Worse in wet weather — especially warm wet weather Cough with expectoration++

consider using homœopathic desensitization alone and see what happens. A synopsis of 3 case histories is given below.

The first was a woman aged 26. She was seen in February 1982. She had had asthma since she was three years old. She also had eczema and hay fever, but both of these had improved spontaneously as she grew older. She, herself, had noted wheezing when she handled cats and dogs. Her main worry was that she was devoted to her long-haired cat. Skin tests showed marked sensitivity to cat fur and dog hair, as well as to horse hair, rabbit fur and grass pollens. She was given three powders of a homœopathic preparation of cat fur and reported 3 months later that there had been no significant wheezing except for a contact with her mother's dog. She was given a homœopathic preparation of dog hair and I did not see her again until October 1983, when she said that she had had no wheezing until the last three weeks when she had had some breathlessness after brushing the stair carpets. She is a very houseproud patient. The skin test to *House dust mite* which had previously been negative was now positive and she was given three doses of this. In February 1984 her eczema became troublesome and this has been the main problem since then. She was seen in November, 1984 when she required a further dose of *House dust mite* (as well as *Psorinum*) and again in August of this year when her eczema had become very troublesome. In fact, by this time she regarded her asthma as something quite incidental and of no great significance, so I am now coping with the homœopathic treatment of her eczema which is really a separate story.

The second was a boy who was four years old when he first came to see me in 1981. There was a very strong atopic family history. He has been wheezing since the age of two years and despite conventional treatment the parents were exhausted by the constant attention which he needed at night. In fact as they all sat in my consulting room it was difficult to tell who was the most exhausted of all of them. Skin tests showed sensitivity to house dust mite and to grass pollens. The homœopathic prescription of *House dust mite* produced a dramatic improvement. So much so that after the fourth week the parents reported that they had had five undisturbed nights. He had a few ups and downs after that and still continued with

TABLE 3 Homœopathic treatment of eczema

Antipsoric remedies	<i>Sulphur</i> <i>Psorinum</i>
Constitutional remedies	<i>Pulsatilla</i> <i>Phosphorus</i> <i>Silicea</i> <i>Calc. phos.</i> <i>Lycopodium</i>
Pathological remedies	<i>Petroleum</i> <i>Graphites</i> <i>Mezereum</i>
Known or suspected allergens (desensitization)	<i>House Dust (Mite)</i> <i>Animal Fur (Dander)</i> <i>Grass Pollens</i> <i>Moulds</i>

some of his conventional treatment (Ventolin Syrup). He has needed occasional doses of *House dust mite* and other remedies (antipsoric), but the overall improvement was maintained until they moved to Milton Keynes in 1984.

I would like to tell you about another boy, but a little older. He was nearly ten when he first came to see me early in 1981. He had all the problems of atopy, asthma and hay fever, but it was the asthma which was causing the most disruption in the family's life. The skin tests showed dust mite sensitivity. A homœopathic prescription of *House dust mite* (and *Petroleum* for his moderate eczema) was followed by initial improvement. In his mother's words, 'in July there has been a great improvement to his asthma' and by October of the same year his mother wrote to say that, on average, six out of seven nights were completely undisturbed. It is of great interest to know the aggravating effect of grass pollens in this boy on his eczema, for in June 1982, after playing with other boys in a field of freshly cut grass, he developed patches of flexural eczema.

A fourth case is of interest as it involves a rather unusual allergen. I normally include this in my skin testing but rarely get a positive reaction. A man of 35 came to see me in July 1983. He had had summer wheezing since 1982 only. This actually started in September, quite unlike grass pollen sensitivity, of course. He was initially given the remedy *Ambrosia* and his wheezing improved, but it was not until March 1984, when I skin-tested him, that I found a truly tremendous reaction to the mould *Alternaria*, as well as a number of lesser reactions. He was given regular weekly doses of a homœopathic preparation of this mould from April 1984 onwards. In August he reported a little wheezing and the dose was increased to once a day. His total episode of wheezing only lasted 2½ weeks, as against the usual 3 months or so, and he has required no conventional treatment whatsoever.

In the treatment of eczema (Table 3) the approach is in many respects very similar, although there are some differences in that remedies are included which have well marked skin symptoms in their provings.

Again we have the great antipsoric remedies *Sulphur* and *Psorinum* and one may consider giving a dose of one or other of these at some stage to counteract the

TABLE 6 *Homœopathic treatment of hay fever and allergic rhinitis***Prevention of seasonal allergy**

- Antipsoric remedies
- Constitutional remedies
- Desensitization using known or suspected allergens

Treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis

- Allium cepa*
- Arsen. alb.*
- Arsen. iodatum*
- Euphrasia*
- Nux vom.*
- Phleum*
- Sabadilla*
- Sticta*
- Teucrium*
- Wyethia*

Non-seasonal allergic rhinitis

- General approach
- Use of specific allergen
- Choice of remedy based on symptom picture

and a dose of this should be given at 3-monthly intervals out of season. A 3-monthly dose of the constitutional remedy should also be given, but this may be difficult for physicians new to homœopathy. I suggest therefore mixed pollen and grasses to be given pre-seasonally, either at monthly intervals or, as I now prefer, daily for two weeks prior to the onset of grass pollination.

Quite a number of remedies are available for the treatment of seasonal pollen allergy, and in view of Dr Reilly's trial in 1983¹ you should add mixed pollens and grasses to your treatment schedule. The trick with the choice of remedy is to try and ensure that some of the general symptoms fit the patient's clinical picture. (Table 7). If there are problems with choosing the appropriate remedy I would suggest that one should at least consider giving mixed pollens and grasses pre-seasonally and possibly also *Psorinum* at intervals during the winter months.

In practice perennial allergic rhinitis is a difficult problem, for conventional medicine has no real cure but a wide spectrum of suppressant treatments. Look carefully at the patient's environment. I have one patient with long-standing allergic rhinitis and nasal polypi who is relatively in remission until they light the solid fuel central heating boiler in the winter. I saw her only last Wednesday. They were on holiday last week and the boiler was not lit until they had been back for 24 hours. Within 12 hours of lighting it her nose was once more congested and she has followed this pattern recurrently for two years (since they moved to their present house). It is important to look for allergens.

Two case histories will illustrate the approach to treatment.

A patient aged 20 came to see me in 1982 with an 18-month history of frequent sneezing on waking in the morning, and streaming discharge from his nose. There was some allergic family history. Skin testing showing sensitivity to dust mite and cat fur (no cat in the house). His prescription was *House dust mite*. He wrote to me

TABLE 7 *Treatment of seasonal pollen allergy*

<i>Allium cepa</i>	Sneezing Watery eyes All discharges non-irritant Much worse in a warm room Much better in cold room and open air
<i>Arsenicum album</i>	All discharges burn Much better in warm room Patient feels chilly Very restless and anxious, especially in early hours of morning
<i>Arsenicum iodatum</i>	Very similar to <i>Ars. alb.</i> but not such a chilly patient
<i>Euphrasia</i>	Acid lachrymation Bland coryza Eyelids stick in mornings Margins of lids red and swollen Worse for warmth
<i>Nux vom.</i>	Nasal discharge. Dry at night, fluent in day Worse warm room Better cold air Very sensitive to noise, etc. Quarrelsome and irritable Throat irritates and feels raw
<i>Phleum</i>	Nose and eyes intensely irritable No marked general symptoms ? Not proved in detail
<i>Sticta pulmonaria</i>	Nose feels blocked and blowing it is useless
<i>Teucrium v. marum</i>	Sneezing Polyps Irritable Irascible
<i>Wyethia</i>	Intense itching of post nares Throat feels swollen Constant desire to swallow

three weeks later to say 'although my nose is still slightly blocked in the morning and I sneeze once or twice, there has been a significant improvement'. Two months later he wrote as follows: 'I am pleased to tell you that my nose has completely cleared up and apart from the occasional sneeze I am not troubled at all'. I heard from him again in March 1983, when his nose had recently been a little troublesome, and the prescription was repeated.

The second patient, seen in 1981, was perhaps not a typical allergic rhinitis in that she was a child aged 8 with chronic catarrh intermittently for years. Her mother had noticed that she sneezed more with the grass pollen season and very much more after bouncing around on her mattress. Skin tests showed a very strongly positive reaction to dust mite and this, of course, was the prescription. There was a considerable improvement and she did not require a further prescription until August 1982. I saw her mother in February 1983 and gave her a further prescription. She said that her daughter had been completely free from trouble until a few weeks ago.

Conclusion

Physicians new to homœopathy should at least be able to make a start with treatment of atopic patients by giving antipsoric remedies and specific allergens. This is not difficult. The use of constitutional remedies, pathological remedies and so on will follow as more experience is gained. I am however going to sound a note of caution. Please learn from my mistakes. In my early days I would instinctively adopt an allopathic approach to treatment. I would see a patient with asthma for homœopathic treatment. Out would come Kent's *Repertory*, opened at the section on Respiration. To start with there is a section on Asthmatic Respiration. 147 remedies are listed; under Difficult Respiration 82 and Wheezing Respiration 62. Matters get worse if you turn to the section headed Chest. Under Constriction there are 85 remedies and under Oppression 129. This approach offers little hope of successful treatment, for until you have acquired experience of the homœopathic materia medica you might just as well blindfold yourself, stick a pin in the list of remedies and hope for the best, but I fear you will become quickly disillusioned with homœopathy.

REFERENCE

1 Reilly DT, Taylor MA. Patient placebo or potency? *A proposed study model with initial findings using homœopathically prepared pollens in hay fever.* *Br Hom J* 1985; **74**: 65.